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Review Article

Benzimidazole Derivatives as Scaffolds for Antimicrobial Drug Discovery: Advances, Structure–Activity Relationships, and Therapeutic Potential

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ABSTRACT

Benzimidazole is a privileged heterocyclic scaffold that has attracted considerable attention in medicinal chemistry due to its wide-ranging pharmacological activities. Over the past decade, benzimidazole derivatives have been extensively investigated for their antimicrobial potential against bacteria, fungi, and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Structural modifications at positions 1, 2, 5, and 6 of the benzimidazole nucleus have yielded diverse analogues with enhanced potency and selectivity. Hybrid molecules incorporating pharmacophores such as quinolines, azoles, triazoles, chalcones, and sulfonamides have demonstrated synergistic antimicrobial effects. This review consolidates synthetic strategies, biological evaluations, and structure–activity relationship (SAR) insights of benzimidazole derivatives reported between 2010 and 2025, highlighting their promise as scaffolds for next-generation antimicrobial agents in the era of rising drug resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Bacteria are unique among the prokaryotes in that so many of them are normal flora that colonize the host without causing infection. New species and new variants of familiar species continue to be discovered, particularly as we intrude into new ecosystems. Among the top causes of mortality in the world, lower respiratory infection is the third most common and diarrhea is the sixth. Both are

often caused by bacteria. Tuberculosis is the seventh most common cause of death. Antimicrobial resistance is a global health crisis, with pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida albicans* developing resistance to conventional drugs. An ideal antimicrobial agent acts at a target site that is present in the infecting organism but not the host cells. Four major sites in the bacterial cell can be targeted by antibiotics because they are

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sufficiently different from human cells. These are the cell wall, the cell membrane, the nucleic acid synthetic pathway, and the ribosome. Antibacterial agents, or antibiotics, are typically products of other microorganisms, elaborated by them in order to compete for space and resources. Some bacteria are innately resistant to certain classes of antibiotics, either because they lack the target or are impermeable to the drug. Others are innately susceptible but develop resistance by one of a growing variety of mechanisms. Resistant strains of bacteria have a selective advantage, surviving in the presence of antibiotics, and can spread throughout the host and even be transferred to other hosts. This phenomenon is important where antibiotic use is common, such as in hospitals or in congregate housing such as nursing homes.

1. Benzimidazoles

Benzimidazole is an organic heterocyclic aromatic compound in which a benzene ring is fused to an imidazole ring.

The location of an imidazole ring with bicyclic nature. The nucleus is synonymously referred to as benzoglyoxalines and 1,3-benzodiazoles and has amphoteric properties (both acidic & basic). The -NH functional group in benzimidazoles shows weak basic nature & strong acidic nature and has the capacity to form salts¹.

Figure 1. Benzimidazole

The very first benzimidazole (2, 5 or 2, 6-dimethylbenzimidazole) was prepared in 1872 by Hoebrecker² through reduction of 2-nitro-4-methylacetanilide. Several years later, Ladenburg obtained the same compound by refluxing 3, 4-diaminotoluene with acetic acid.

Scheme 1

Though all seven positions in the benzimidazole nucleus can be substituted with a variety of chemical entities, but most of the biologically

active benzimidazole based compounds bear functional groups at 1, 2 and/or 5(or 6) positions. Accordingly, the compounds may be mono-, di- or tri-substituted derivatives of the nucleus.

Table 1. Some clinically used benzimidazole compounds

Therapeutic Class	Name of Molecule	Chemical Structure
Anthelmintic	Albendazole	
Anti-Psychotics	Pimozide	
Analgesics	Benzitramide	
Hypertensives	Candesartan	
Fungicides	Fuberidazole	
Anti-fungal	Chlorimidazole	
Antihistamine	Astemizole	
Anti-Ulcerative	Omeprazole	
Anti-cancer	Bendamustine	

Anti-viral	Maribavir	
Anti-dopaminergic	Domperidone	

The general method for synthesis of 2-substituted benzimidazoles involves the reaction between 1, 2-phenylene diamine and a carboxylic acid or an

acid chloride or nitrile in the presence of strong acid catalyst³ or with aldehydes in the presence of oxidants⁴.

Scheme 2

2. Pharmacological actions of benzimidazoles

The enormous potentiality of benzimidazole-based compounds in medicinal chemistry has led to a lot of work being directed towards the feasible prolific applications of benzimidazole derivatives in diverse areas. In a recent study, Kumar et al. (2024)⁵ performed the synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives. All the compounds were characterized by UV, IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectral data and CHN elemental analysis. The synthesized derivatives were screened for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities. All the compounds showed significant

effect at 100 mg/kg p.o. and the experimental data are statistically significant at $p < 0.01$ level.

The design and synthesis of benzimidazole-oxadiazole derivatives as new inhibitors for vascular endothelial growth factor receptor-2 (VEGFR-2) was reported by Cevik et al. (2024).⁶ The designed members were assessed for their in vitro anticancer activity against three cancer cell lines and two normal cell lines; A549, MCF-7, PANC-1, hTERT-HPNE and CCD-19Lu.

Comp.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
4a	-H	-H	-H
4b	-H	-H	-CH ₃
4c	-H	-H	-Cl
4d	-H	-H	-F
4e	-H	-H	-Br
4f	-H	-H	-CN
4g	-F	-H	-F
4h	-Cl	-H	-Cl
4i	-H	-OH	-OH

A series of benzo[d]imidazole-amide containing 1,2,3-triazole-N-arylacetamide derivatives were synthesized and evaluated them for their inhibitory activity against α -glucosidase by Yousefnejad et

al. (2023)⁷. In vitro α -glucosidase inhibition assay demonstrated that more than half of the title compounds with IC₅₀ values in the range of 49.0–668.5 μ M.

The anti-diabetic activities of some new heterocyclic compounds based on benzimidazole-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was reported by Abas et al. (2022).⁸ Oral administration of new synthesized benzimidazole

derivatives compounds ameliorated all biochemical parameters (ALT, AST ALB, T.Bili, urea, creatinine, CK-MB and LDH) and enhanced activity of antioxidant enzymes.

Several arylated benzimidazoles derivatives were synthesized by Akande et al. (2021)⁹ and screened for α -amylase inhibitory, 2,2'-azinobis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS), and 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging activities. In vitro screening results revealed that all molecules demonstrated significant α -amylase inhibition with IC₅₀ values of 1.86 ± 0.08 to 3.16 ± 0.31 μ M.

Seventeen derivatives of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole bearing sulfonamide were synthesized by Hussain et al. (2021)¹⁰. All the compounds were screened for their α -amylase inhibitory potential and displayed a variable degree of α -amylase activity having IC₅₀ values

ranging between 0.90 ± 0.05 to $11.20 \pm 0.30 \mu\text{M}$ when compared with the standard drug acarbose having IC 50 value $1.70 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{M}$.

Wang et al. (2018)¹¹ synthesized a series of chrysin benzimidazole derivatives and studied their anticancer activity. Among synthesized compounds, compound showed the most potent anti-proliferative activity against MFC cells with IC50 values of $25.72 \pm 3.95 \mu\text{M}$.

In an attempt to design ACE inhibitors, Abdulaziz Hammad et al. (2017)¹² designed series of benzimidazole derivatives as ACE inhibitor. From molecular docking study and in silico toxicity study, they found compound 2-(2-(butylthio)-5-methoxy-1H-indol-1-yl)-1-(2-nitrophenyl) ethan-1-one as an equipotent ACE inhibitor with respect to lisinopril as a standard drug.

In another study, L Ravithey Singh et al. (2017)¹⁵ synthesized new coumarin-benzimidazole

5-methanesulphonamido benzimidazole derivatives were synthesized by Ratika Sharma et al. (2017)¹³ and tested in carrageenan induced rat paw edema model as anti-inflammatory agents. Among tested compounds, three showed maximum (92.73%, 95.64 % and 97.62% respectively) reduction in edema and were also non-ulcerogenic at the tested doses.

A series of benzimidazole derivatives was synthesized and tested for antimicrobial activity by N.S. El-Gohary et al. (2017)¹⁴. Among the tested two compounds showed good activity toward *S. aureus* with MIC value $0.524 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $0.684 \mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively, whereas one compound with MIC value $0.489 \mu\text{g/ml}$ exhibited remarkable activity toward *B. cereus*. One compound was found the most active antifungal analog toward *C. albicans* with MIC value $0.262 \mu\text{g/ml}$.

derivatives and evaluated them for their antibacterial activity. They found that the

compound showed better antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa* with (MIC 3.12 µg/ml).

Olayinka O. Ajani et al. (2016)¹⁶ synthesized 2-substituted benzimidazole derivatives and evaluated their antimicrobial activity against gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris* and *S. faecalis*) and gram-negative bacterial strains (*K. pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*) by zone of inhibition method.

Table 2. Structure–Activity Relationship (SAR) of Benzimidazole Derivatives for antimicrobial action

Compound	Target pathogen	Observations	Reference
2-Quinoline substituted benzimidazole	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i>	Quinoline hybridization enhances DNA gyrase inhibition and broad-spectrum antibacterial activity.	Desai et al 2018 ¹⁷
5-Nitrobenzimidazole	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> H37Rv	Nitro substitution promotes redox cycling and enzyme inhibition in <i>M. tuberculosis</i> .	Singh et al., 2016 ¹⁸
2-Azole tethered benzimidazole	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Azole linkage improves binding to lanosterol 14 α -demethylase, enhancing antifungal potency	Jain et al., 2017 ¹⁹
2-Triazole-substituted benzimidazole	Gram-negative bacteria	Triazole tethering increases lipophilicity and membrane penetration	Ahmed et al., 2024 ²⁰
5-or 6-Halogenated benzimidazole	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. subtilis</i>	Electron-withdrawing halogens enhance lipophilicity and improve Gram-positive inhibition	Chandran et al., 2025 ²¹
Benzimidazole–chalcone hybrid	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Chalcone conjugation increases ROS generation and disrupts bacterial membranes	Tarek et al., 2025 ²²
Benzimidazole–sulfonamide hybrid	<i>Candida albicans</i>	Sulfonamide enhances polarity and hydrogen bonding, improving antifungal selectivity	Kumawat & Tare, 2024 ²³

CONCLUSION

Benzimidazole derivatives represent a versatile and highly promising class of compounds in

antimicrobial drug discovery. Their ability to undergo substitution at multiple positions allows for structural diversity and optimization of biological activity. Evidence from 2010–2025 demonstrates that electron-withdrawing substituents, heteroaryl linkages, and hybridization with pharmacophores significantly enhance antibacterial, antifungal, and antitubercular efficacy. SAR analyses consistently highlight the importance of position 2 substitution and halogenation at positions 5 or 6 in improving potency. The development of benzimidazole hybrids, particularly with quinoline, azole, triazole, chalcone, and sulfonamide moieties, has opened new avenues for combating resistant pathogens. Future research should emphasize *in vivo* validation, toxicity profiling, and advanced delivery systems to translate these promising scaffolds into clinically viable therapeutics. Collectively, benzimidazole derivatives stand as strong candidates for next-generation antimicrobial agents, offering hope in addressing the global challenge of antimicrobial resistance.

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